

Growing Inequality:
a Novel Integration of
transformations research

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
of the European Union

D7.3 Scientific paper and popular booklet: Selected core future scenarios and outcomes

WP7 Future scenarios: design, analysis and outcomes

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Associate Work Package:	WP7
Lead Beneficiary:	TNO
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Document Summary

Document type:	<i>Report</i>
Title:	<i>D7.3 Scientific paper and popular booklet: Selected core future scenarios and outcomes</i>
Author/s:	<i>Gerben Hulsegge, Marieke van den Tooren, Steven Dhondt and others</i>
Reviewer/s:	<i>See separate reports in this PDF</i>
Date:	<i>July 28th, 2024</i>
Document status:	<i>SUBMITTED</i>
Keywords:	<i>globalization; digital transformation; socio-economic inequality; skills mismatches</i>
Version:	<i>1.0</i>
Document level:	<i>Public</i>

Comment

This deliverable consists of two parts: (1) a scientific paper and (2) a popular booklet. Both reports deal with selected core future scenarios and outcomes. Both results have different purposes and audiences.

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